

MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF AZERBAIJANI ROMANTICISM

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Abstract. *The romanticism movement, one of the main trends in Azerbaijani literature of the 20th century, has taken its place in our literature as a literary trend that is distinguished in terms of its ideological directions and aesthetic characteristics and essentially requires a new form and content. The main feature that distinguished this trend from other trends was the universal ideas and important aesthetic characteristics it encompassed. The article, based on the work of Azerbaijani romantics, has been involved in the study of the specific main ideological directions of romanticism and its aesthetic characteristics have been investigated.*

Key words: *romanticism, literary trends, literature, aesthetics, artistic examples.*

Аннотация. *Романтизм, одно из основных направлений азербайджанской литературы XX века, занял в нашей литературе свое место как самобытное по своим идейным установкам и эстетическим особенностям литературное направление, по сути требующее новой формы и содержания. Главным, что отличало это движение от других, были универсальные идеи и важные эстетические характеристики, которые оно включало. В статье рассматриваются основные идейные направления романтизма на основе творчества азербайджанских романтиков, рассматриваются их эстетические особенности.*

Ключевые слова: *романтизм, литературные течения, литература, эстетика, художественные образцы.*

The literary movement of Romanticism emerged in Europe at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. Although this movement benefited from the ancient and ancient traditions of the East, Romanticism was able to be formed as a movement with its own specific literary and aesthetic principles and object. Romantics preferred a universal, philosophical program and logic. They kept the inner world of man more in the center of attention. In fact, the interest in the inner world of man, the world of the heart with the participation of Romanticism, was not their individual style. It was a step forward from the place of other movements in the human problem that became the central theme of this literature. The Romanticism movement that emerged in Azerbaijani literature at the beginning of the 20th century was more national in its ideological direction and aesthetic essence.

The core of the interest of Azerbaijani romantics has always been the human problem. It is not easy to find a second object that occupies a place in the object of romantics' thought as much as fate. M.Hadi, H.Javid, A.Seihat, A.Shaig, starting from the first years of their creativity, thought about the solution of this problem and raised their ideas and considerations on this to a height characteristic of romanticism.

The value given to man in romanticism also had a deep meaning. Romantics did not simply talk about a general person, the concept of a person. For them, there was a specific person. M.Hadi noted in one of his articles that you, who are not worried about the suffering of

others, calling you a person is not a serious understatement. What the author wants to emphasize here is that a person cannot remain outside of society, he must think about the troubles and sufferings that society gives him.

Romantics, as a rule, always contrasted the East and the West in their articles and works. The prominent scientist, academician M.J. Jafarov, while discussing the ideological features of Azerbaijani romanticism, extensively touched upon the issue of the West and the East. M.J. Jafarov noted, "One of the sweetest, romantic dreams cherished by Azerbaijani romantics was the dream of a life similar to the Western cultural life in the East. Their dream was not to escape from cultural life, but rather to achieve cultural life, to join modern culture." [1, 118]

Since 1905, the search for a new poetic style began to manifest itself in literature. As a result, in order to spread the theoretical and aesthetic foundations of the newly formed romantic poetry at that time, and to give a new direction to Azerbaijani poetry, Mahammad Hadi, Abbas Sahhat and other well-known poets began to work actively in this field. The main reason for this was that in 1890-1905, Azerbaijani realistic prose and dramaturgy developed significantly, harmonized with modern life, and moved in a direction consistent with the spirit of the people. Undoubtedly, this development was the result of the tireless work and works created by such great thinkers as Jalil Mammadguluzadeh, Abdurrahim bey Hagverdiyev, Najaf bey Vezirov, Nariman Narimanov, Mirza Fatali Akhundzadeh. However, Azerbaijani poetry lagged far behind this development. Epigonism prevailed in the field of poetic creativity. This situation led Azerbaijani poetry, which has ancient and rich traditions, to distance itself from its classical heritage. At that time, poetry could not keep up with modern life, did not respond to the needs of the people, and was helpless in finding solutions to their troubles and problems. This deplorable state of our national poetry and its lagging behind the requirements of the time were already causing serious concern in literary circles, and serious debates were taking place in the press regarding this.

As in world romantic literature, in Azerbaijani romantic literature of the early 20th century, the general philosophy of love acts as an expression of the aesthetic ideal of the romantics. Studies on romanticism note that the idealization of female love, which is characteristic of classical love lyrics, and the transformation of love suffering into the main, leading motif of the lyrics are very rare here. In romantic poetry, love lyrics often became a symbolic means expressing certain philosophical and political views. This, first of all, ensured the artistic generalization of the love for the people to which one belongs at the level of love for humanity in general. In H. Javid's poem "Girl's School", in response to the question "Do you have any other loved ones?", the line of the schoolgirl "my mother, my grandfather, my teacher, and all people" reflects the essence of the philosophy of love in romanticism in all its breadth. The fact that H. Javid's poem "My God" does not specifically mention any lover, but rather speaks of love and beauty in general in a broad sense is a perfect echo of the general philosophy of love in romanticism.

In Romanticism, the motifs of human philosophy, which were brought to the forefront by the theme of universal love, were developed and brought to the level of expressing generalized human ideas in romantic literature. A. Shaig's poem "We are all a particle of a sun" is the most beautiful example of the love of humanity and human humanism of Azerbaijani romantics.

In A. Shaig's poem "We are all particles of the sun", which is considered a manifesto of the ideas of humanism, nationality, and humanity, religious, national, and racial discrimination among people is rejected, and people are invited to unity and solidarity. In fact, these are the moments that are evident in the creativity of all romantics. As we mentioned above, for

romantics, the issue of man and his fate has always been at the forefront. Therefore, they have always worked on this problem in their creativity, and universal ideas have formed the main goal of their works.

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